

Metal Complexes of Dithiodiglycollic Acid and Its Use as New Analytical Reagent for the Amperometric Determination of Ce(IV), Fe(III), Hg(II) and Hg(I)

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Amperometric titrations of Ce(IV), Fe(III), Hg(I) and Hg(II) at an applied potential of 0.0V, -0.6V, -0.5V and 0.55V respectively using dropping mercury indicator electrode, against dithiodiglycollic acid have been carried out. Solutions containing as little as 10 ppm of metal ion can be accurately determined with an error of $\pm 0.5\%$. The metal complexes could be isolated in the solid forms and the combining ratio was also determined from their chemical analysis and their structures were confirmed from their i.r. spectra and magnetic measurements.

SURVEY of the existing literature revealed that nothing has so far been done on the metal complexes of dithiodiglycollic acid. The present communication deals with the amperometric determination of Ce(IV), Fe(III), Hg(II) and Hg(I) using dithiodiglycollic acid and the composition and structure of the reaction products formed on mixing the reactants in aqueous solutions.

Experimental

Physical measurements : as previously reported¹

Reagents and solutions : The solutions of ferric nitrate, mercuric chloride, potassium nitrate, potassium hydroxide, dithiodiglycollic acid (Evans, U.S.A.) in double distilled water, ceric ammonium nitrate in 0.5 N sulphuric acid and mercurous nitrate in dilute nitric acid were prepared. All the reagents were of A.R. quality.

Results and Discussion

The pK_1 and pK_2 of the dithiodiglycollic acid as determined by potentiometric half titration method² (20 ml. of 0.0033 M reagent vs 0.1 M KOH) were 3.20 and 10.64 1 : 2 (M : L) stoichiometry of Fe(III) complex and 1 : 1 of Ce(IV), Hg(II) and Hg(I) complex was found in the concentration range from 0.00083 M to 0.0033 M by amperometric titrations carried out at -0.6 V and 0.0 V, -0.55 V and -0.5 V respectively.

Procedure for the determination : A measured volume of standard metal solution, to give the desired concentration, was introduced into a 100 ml. flask; to this was added 50 ml. of 1M KNO₃ and the solution diluted to the mark with the solvent. An aliquot (20 ml.) of this solution was transferred to a polarographic cell, deaerated by bubbling pure

nitrogen and a potential of 0.0V, -0.6V, -0.55V and -0.5V in the determination of Ce(IV), Fe(III), Hg(II) and Hg(I) respectively vs SCE was applied, using as an indicator electrode. The pH of the solution was adjusted between 1.0 and 2.0, 2.5 and 4.0, 5.0 and 6.0 and 1.0 and 2.5 by the addition of HNO₃ or KOH in the case of (Ce(IV), Fe(III), Hg(II) and Hg(I) respectively. Measured volumes of the reagent solution were added and after each addition, the solution was stirred by bubbling nitrogen gas and the current measured after an interval of few minutes until the precipitates formed were settled.

Solution containing as little as 140 ppm of metal ion be accurately determined and from 10 ppm to 140 ppm of the metal ion can be determined with an accuracy of $\pm 0.5\%$.

To know the polarographic reduction behaviour of the ligand, a polarogram of the solution of dithiodiglycollic acid (0.0022M) containing potassium nitrate (0.5M) as supporting electrolyte and gelatin (0.003%) as maxima suppressor, was taken which indicated the presence of two waves. The half wave potential ($E_{1/2}$) and diffusion current (i_d) of the first wave was found to be -0.7V and 29.25 μ A and of second wave -1.3V and 10.5 μ A respectively. The plateau of the first wave (complete diffusion) was found beyond -1.0V and of second wave beyond -1.5V.

Interferences : Interference studies were carried out by taking an aliquot of the metal solution, adding 5-10 fold excess of the foreign ion and titrating as described above, Li(I), Na(I), K(I), Rb(I), Tl(I), Mg(II), Ca(II), Sr(II), Ba(II), Fe(II), Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II), Zn(II), Pd(II), Pb(II), Cd(II), Mn(II), Sn(II), Al(III), Cr(III), As(III), Sb(III), Bi(III), In(III), Ga(III), Ir(III), Au(III), Sn(IV), Pt(IV), rare earth

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